

DiFX Outputbands

Technical Report Revision A

Jan Wagner, MPIfR

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Efforts in astronomical (sub)mm-VLBI and geodetic VLBI to increase the sensitivity and observing bandwidth can run into inconsistent frequency setups within the network. The phased ALMA and NOEMA interferometric arrays have by design a fixed channelization that is different from other VLBI stations. Similarly, stations have a choice between various (ultra)wideband backends such as BRAND, Bluring, DBBC3, R2DBE, OCTAD, and others, that despite top-level specifications, e.g., VGOS and IVS, do not always support a standardized common observing mode. Furthermore, BRAND uses station specific frequency setups to avoid local in-channel RFI.

These affect the correlation and a priori calibration of the VLBI observations. Although software correlators like DiFX-2 are flexible enough to handle such observations the standard FITS-IDI and HOPS data formats and data reduction tasks are not. Here I describe a spectral processing step that was implemented in DiFX-2 that recovers an uniform frequency setup and that restores compatibility with FITS-IDI and HOPS formats.

Additional details regarding calibration and the results of VLBI test observations are outside the scope of this report and the subject of a paper.

Revision History

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1 Preamble

This technical report describes the current implementation and status of DiFX outputbands. A co-authored paper is intended to follow once the primary drivers of this software extension work, namely the NOEMA Phasing Project and BRAND-EVN receiver project, have gone on-sky and provided data from the first VLBI test observations.

2 Introduction

This document describes the implementation of a new correlator capability, “outputbands”, in the DiFX software correlator (Deller et al. 2007, 2011). The open source DiFX software correlator has been widely adopted by the astronomical and geodetic

VLBI communities. It is in production use at several large VLBI networks including the VLBA, LBA, GMVA¹, EHT², and others, and supports numerous processing modes such as multiple phase centers, near field observations, line/continuum VLBI, space VLBI, pulsar VLBI, and radio transient searches. DiFX from version 2.5 onwards also supports “zoom bands”. These are narrower bands which fall within the recorded frequency bands and are extracted by discrete Fourier transform (DFT) during correlation.

Observations where stations have slightly different frequency setups are routinely correlated using zoom bands. If frequency setups differ significantly, however, correlation cannot be handled via zoom bands alone. This happens in observations that include several phased radio interferometer arrays such as the SMA, ALMA, and NOEMA. Being designed independently and for interferometric observations rather than VLBI, their characteristics are uncommon for VLBI; recorded bands are narrow, may overlap, sampling rates may not be a power-of-2 in MHz. Lesser incompatibilities may also occur at VLBI stations that use direct RF sampling or full IF sampling systems such as BRAND³, CSIRO Bluering, Effelsberg EDD. BRAND in particular is anticipated to provide consistent 128 MHz wide channels, but tuning will differ not only between BRAND-equipped and non-BRAND antennas, but also between BRAND antennas themselves.

Between BRAND antennas the radio frequency interference (RFI) situation will be quite different resulting in different usable parts of the radio band. Rather than just one or very few frequency setups, as is the standard in present day VLBI correlation, a BRAND network will always have a different frequency setup for each telescope. Channels can be shifted to avoid strong in-channel RFI that would make the entire channel unusable. This station specific tuning complicates the correlation of the data significantly.

In the above cases, VLBI experiments end up with two or more stations mismatched significantly enough as to require DiFX zoom band correlation with an excessive number of zoom bands that are narrow (e.g., 128 x 1 MHz zoom bands) or that have unequal bandwidths. The DiFX correlator itself can handle such unusual setups, but the resulting data are incompatible with the standard VLBI data formats of FITS-IDI⁴ and HOPS/Mk4⁵. Additional processing is needed to recover a frequency structure for the visibility data that is compatible with these data formats, and certain additional steps are needed during a priori calibration.

3 Method

The new DiFX “outputbands” processing overcomes the aforementioned issues that stem from by-design frequency setup differences in certain VLBI observations. The method

¹Global mm-VLBI Array, <https://www3.mpifr-bonn.mpg.de/div/vlbi/globalmm/>

²Event Horizon Telescope, <https://eventhorizontelescope.org/>

³Digital ultra-wideband 1.5-15.5 GHz receiver for EVN VLBI; EU H2020 grant 730562, RadioNet JRA WP6 BRAND-EVN, <https://radiowiki.mpifr-bonn.mpg.de/doku.php?id=jra:brand>

⁴FITS-IDI see AIPS Memo 114 <https://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov/registry/fitsidi/AIPSMEM114.PDF>

⁵HOPS see <https://www.haystack.mit.edu/haystack-observatory-postprocessing-system-hops>

Figure 1: Example of a mixed frequency setup similar to the first GMVA-ALMA observation of Sgr A* in 2017. Initially requested 58 MHz wide zoom bands were not possible directly due to an inadvertent narrow 32 MHz setup at two stations (red boxes). Manual DiFX 2.5 zoom bands (grey boxes) were post-processed or “de-zoomed” to recover 58 MHz wide IFs and allow data to be exported as FITS-IDI. Only one such IF is shown here (dark grey box).

is illustrated in Figure 1, using the GMVA-ALMA 2017 campaign as an example of the steps that assemble new frequency bands of equal bandwidth out of recorded bands.

Visibilities in the synthesized frequency bands (outputbands) are produced as follows. First, recorded bands are split in the frequency domain into suitably fine-grained spectral slices by defining “zoom” bands that are used in a normal DiFX 2.5/2.6 correlation. Next, visibility data of neighbouring zoom bands are concatenated along the frequency axis, i.e., are “de-zoomed” to form wideband visibilities. Lastly, a spectral averaging step may be added to reach the PI-requested spectral resolution. The final visibility data cover the original observed sky frequency range without being restricted to the boundaries of the actual recorded bands. In addition, they have a FITS-compatible uniform bandwidth and are from only a few frequency bands, thereby achieving compatibility with the FITS-IDI and HOPS data formats.

There are two implementations of the processing above. The first is a standalone utility (*difx2difx.py*) that works offline on the correlator output. The second implementation is integrated into the DiFX correlator (DiFX SVN branch *Outputbands*) and is applied online during correlation such that as illustrated in Figure 2 the temporary data files associated with the offline method are avoided.

4 Offline Implementation

A Python-based spectral reassembly script (*difx2difx.py*) was implemented in 2017 and is in production use for GMVA correlation. The script can be found in the public DiFX source code repository⁶.

⁶<https://www.atnf.csiro.au/vlbi/dokuwiki/doku.php/difx/installation>

Figure 2: Processing stages in the offline (top) and online (bottom) implementations of outputbands. The former converts data of a standard DiFX 2.5/2.6 zoom band correlation, the latter avoids temporary data, but relies on a modified DiFX correlator.

4.1 Details and Script Usage

Given a set of DiFX visibility data files and a configuration file, *difax2difax.py* concatenates the zoom bands present in the original data and frequency averages the resulting visibility data before final output (cf. Figure 1). The script requires a configuration file with certain settings that are largely self-explanatory. An example is given below:

```

[config]
stitch_basefreqs: 86151.109375, 86209.703125, 86268.296875, 86326.890625
target_bw: 58.000
target_nchan: 3712
target_chavg: 32
stitch_antennas: AA, EB, EF, YS, PV, BR, FD, KP, LA, NL, OV, PT, GB
stitch_nstokes: 4
verbose: false
[phases_deg]
AA = -32.0, -64.0, +16.0, ... # optional; phase of each recorded band
YS = +180.0, -180.0, +180.0, ...
  
```

The script processes data from a normal DiFX zoom band correlation. Correlation must be set up manually. The new DiFX script *autoBands.py* run on the VEX file can aid in the placement of outputbands and the manual definition of zoom bands. An important constraint is that the DiFX correlation must be configured with groups of zoom bands, manually defined such that the first zoom of a group starts at one of the user-provided outputband frequencies listed under the *stitch_basefreqs* setting.

Once the experiment has been correlated with DiFX, the zoom band output data can be processed into outputband visibility data using *difax2difax.py*:

```
difx2difx.py [-m|--meta-only] <configfile.cfg> <difx basename>
```

The script creates an updated DiFX *.input* file that adds metadata details of the new outputbands, and also creates a new visibility data set. The produced files are:

```
<difx basename>D2D.input      Updated DiFX job metadata
<difx basename>D2D/DIFX_*    New visibility data
```

The new visibility data set contains visibilities and autocorrelations of the outputbands only. These have a consistent bandwidth. The original (temporary) zoom bands are not included. This new visibility data set can be converted into FITS-IDI and HOPS formats with the standard *difx2fits* or *difx2mark4* converter programs, respectively.

4.2 Evaluation of Offline Processing for non-GMVA Observations

After its initial application in salvaging the GMVA-ALMA 2017 campaign on Sgr A* (Issaoun et al. 2019; project MB007), offline processing was integrated into production correlation of subsequent GMVA sessions. Use cases outside of GMVA emerged later, namely, EHT VLBI with additional phased arrays, and BRAND-EVN VLBI.

To evaluate the feasibility of outputbands processing for BRAND, I generated representative visibility data via a “simulated” DiFX 2.6 correlation⁷ with 128 MHz recorded bands that were offset by multiples of 1 MHz at different stations to emulate avoidance of local RFI. Synthetic raw data were correlated in 1 MHz wide zoom bands at a spectral resolution of 125 kHz. After correlation the visibilities were assembled using *difx2difx.py*. This successfully produced 32 MHz wide outputbands that covered the common sky frequency range. More extensive simulations as well as tests with on-sky VLBI data remain to be carried out once a BRAND receiver is commissioned.

Another use case is EHT VLBI when phased NOEMA joins in year 2021. These campaigns will likely have a frequency setup similar to the complexity shown in Figure 1; single dish stations with 2 x 2048 MHz or 1 x 4096 MHz, NOEMA with 64 x 64 MHz, and ALMA with 6.25%-overlapped 2 x 32 x 62.5 MHz recorded bands. Using EHT 2018 Mark 6 recordings and simulated phased NOEMA data, I evaluated the performance of offline outputbands processing via custom zoom band correlation under DiFX 2.6 followed by *difx2difx.py* postprocessing.

Tests with different output bandwidth settings and comparisons also to plain non-outputband visibilities yielded consistent EHT VLBI fringes. However, a large amount of temporary visibility data is produced prior to the *difx2difx.py* stage. This is because a fine spectral resolution of 15.625 kHz is required first to match ALMA recorded overlapped bands and their peculiar tuning against other EHT stations. This is followed by spectral averaging by factor 32 to a target resolution of 0.5 MHz (EHT 2017, EHT 2018). Normally this done during correlation, but for offline postprocessing this step must occur late; some zoom bands may have a prime or otherwise unaverageable number of spectral channels. Only after assembly into an outputband is the total number of channels

⁷Simulated correlation involves a VEX file describing the hypothetical observation and a correlation setup that makes use of the fake data source facility supported by DiFX.

divisible by the averaging factor (see also Figure 6). The high spectral resolution data increases the network load in the cluster, write-out data volume, and disk usage by factor 32. DiFX run time at the Bonn correlator was roughly doubled, and the temporary data that are input to *difx2difx.py* occupied on the order of one terabyte per observing day. These overheads may be borderline acceptable for the rare once-yearly multi-day EHT campaigns. For archival of visibility data from all steps, however, as required on grounds of reproducibility and accounting, large data volumes can be prohibitive.

5 Native Implementation in the DiFX Correlator

The advantages of offline processing (§ 4) are simplicity and correlation with unmodified DiFX 2.x releases. However, offline processing incurs network and storage overheads as mentioned earlier. A native implementation was thus added into DiFX with a particular eye on the use case of EHT VLBI with phased ALMA and NOEMA. Details of the native implementation and its usage are provided in the next sections.

The modifications to DiFX to support native outputbands processing were kept to a minimum. The visibility data format remains unchanged, configuration file formats likewise except for the addition of two new optional parameters and one new flag file. Software modifications included a minor extension of the correlation setup program (*vex2difx*), non-architectural changes to the correlator program (*mpifxcorr*), and extension of a library (*difxio*). Converter utilities (*difx2fits*, *difx2mark4*) were updated negligibly by calls to a new frequency lookup function in *difxio*.

5.1 Extension of v2d file parameters

For existing correlation jobs the DiFX configuration file (v2d file) remains backwards compatible with DiFX 2.6. New correlation jobs that want to use the outputband feature need to specify the following optional parameter:

SETUP section: *outputBandwidth* = [*auto* | *<bandwidth>* in MHz]

When the *outputBandwidth* parameter is specified and has a setting of *auto*, a suitable maximal bandwidth for outputbands is auto-detected based on the observed sky frequencies and recorded bandwidths of all stations (*VEX* file *\$FREQ* section). Alternatively, the output bandwidth can be set explicitly to a *<bandwidth>*, e.g. *58.5* for 58.5 MHz.

Note that there are no guarantees that an explicit output bandwidth can indeed be synthesized for the frequency setup given in the *VEX* file. *Vex2difx* will show an error in this case, and a different bandwidth setting should be tried. Further note that for simplicity, different from zoom band syntax, the current outputband implementation does not allow entry of explicit outband edge frequencies; the placement of outputbands is automatic (§ 5.2) and accounts for possibly overlapped recorded bands (§ 5.4).

A second optional *v2d* file parameter, *gainOffsets*, was added (but will likely be removed again) that allows amplitudes in the recorded bands to be rescaled:

ANTENNA section: *gainOffsets* = $\langle \Delta\text{gain of freq 1}, \Delta\text{gain of freq 2}, \dots \rangle$ with $\Delta\text{gain} \in [-1, 1]$ that are relative to unity gain, i.e., $\Delta\text{gain} = 0$ is neutral.

With the above parameter one can manually bandpass-align all recorded bands of an antenna. Similarly, existing DiFX 2.6 parameter *freqClockOffs* can be used to delay-align (phase-align) all recorded bands of an antenna. Jointly these parameters may be used to compensate for discontinuities that may occur inside an assembled outputband (§ 6, § 7). However, the manual approach is tedious and *gainOffsets* in particular will affect the a priori amplitude calibration. The preferred approach is to carry out a station-based complex bandpass calibration during postprocessing (§ 7).

5.2 Automatic Zoom Band Generation

In both modes of the *outputBandwidth* parameter (auto, or explicit bandwidth) *vex2difx* introduces new zoom bands as necessary. Manual zoom band definitions are also allowed.

The process that generates automatic zoom band definitions is illustrated in Figure 3. First, the sky frequency range covered by the recorded bands (*VEX* file) is segmented into spectral slices, dictated by the edges of the recorded bands. Slices with insufficient stations are discarded. Next, new outputbands are grown from spectrally adjacent slices. The amount of spectrum required to cover one full outputband (target bandwidth in the *v2d* file) is iteratively gathered from remaining spectral slices. Exact coverage is accomplished by defining new zoom bands (e.g., *zf0*, *zf1*, and *zf2* in Fig. 3) within each spectral slice such that this set of zooms jointly spans one full outputband (e.g., *IF0* in Fig. 3). The zoom bands may be identical to a spectral slice, such as in Fig. 3, but some may also represent a narrower portion of one slice. Any trailing leftover portion of a slice is utilized for the next outputband. The process is repeated for additional outputbands (e.g., *zf3*, *zf4*, and *zf5* produce *IF1* in Fig. 3) until no useable spectral slices remain. The new zoom band definitions are propagated into the DiFX job descriptor *input* file(s), together with new frequency entries that represent the outputbands.

The *input* files can be inspected with the utility *printDiFXInput.py*. It displays a summary of all DiFX frequencies (recorded, zoom, and outputband), the baselines to process, the recorded and zoom bands per baseline to correlate, and the explicit or implicit mapping of those zoom bands to target outputbands.

To aid scripted calibration under CASA and ParselTongue it is intended that *vex2difx* will produce a programmatically parseable summary file that would describe the zoom composition of outputbands. It is not yet implemented. For the time being, this info can be gleaned only from the terminal output of *vex2difx* and *printDiFXInput.py*.

5.3 Extension of DiFX input File Syntax

In all DiFX versions a job descriptor file (*input* file) dictates how *mpifxcorr* carries out a correlation job. The file is written by *vex2difx* and is not intended for user editing. It holds several tables, amongst others a frequency table with all VEX and DiFX fre-

Figure 3: Automatic zoom band generation. Spectral regions are defined by the joint set of all recorded band edges (*VEX* file). *Vex2difx* fills these regions with new zoom bands that add up to the requested output bandwidth (*v2d* file). Each zoom band has one target outputband. This $N : 1$ mapping is stored in the *input* file used by the *mpifxcorr* correlator that then assembles visibility data accordingly during correlation, e.g., *zf0*, *zf1*, and *zf2* assemble to *IF0*.

quencies and their properties: sky frequency, bandwidth, and sideband. Visibility data records in DiFX output refer to frequency table indices. Regardless of origin (recorded band, zoom band, or outputband) the visibility records can be treated identically; converters from DiFX to HOPS and FITS-IDI are not aware of the internal type of band.

The updated *vex2difx* adds frequency details of the zoom bands and associated outputbands to the normal frequency table of the *input* file. Visibility records in correlator output continue to refer to frequency table indices. An inconsequential difference is that in the DiFX outputbands version these all refer to outputband frequencies, while under DiFX 2.6 they refer to recorded and/or explicit zoom frequencies.

The outputband planning process also constructs the necessary zoom(s)-to-outputband mappings. These must be stored in the *input* file to instruct the *mpifxcorr* correlation. Because the standard DiFX 2.6 *input* file does not support mappings the syntax had to be extended. Mappings are now added to the baseline table using an optional keyword, *TARGET FREQ*, as illustrated on the right of Figure 4.

The default is the one-to-one map. It reproduces DiFX 2.6 behaviour.

5.4 Overlapped Recorded Bands

A corner case for automatic zoom bands occurs for overlapped recorded bands like at ALMA; the same spectral region is redundantly covered by two recorded bands.

Vex2difx attempts to minimize bandpass related artefacts by choosing the zoom band that is located the farthest from either edge of the two containing recorded bands. Values for the *input* file keywords *D/STREAM A BAND* and *D/STREAM B BAND* (Fig. 4) that refer to pairs of bands to cross-correlate are updated to reflect the “best” zoom band choice.

Figure 4: Syntax extension of the *input* file BASELINE table by a new keyword, *TARGET FREQ*. The colored boxes depict different bands. The existing keywords *D/STREAM A BAND* and *D/STREAM B BAND* specify band-pairs to cross correlate. Under DiFX 2.6 the result is outputted as-is and carries the same frequency tag as the bands (left), whereas under DiFX outputbands the results contribute to explicit frequency tags (right). Their placement within outputbands (arrows on the right) is implicit, via sky frequency, see § 5.5. Note: *bands* in current context are frequency table indices and a polarization label, e.g., datastream 0 band 10 may be frequency table entry 0 in RCP, band 11 frequency 20 in RCP, etc, resolved via the existing DATASTREAM table (not show here).

A similar optimization, currently not implemented, would be for the spectral slice determination process (§ 5.2) to detect overlapped bands and insert slice boundaries not at the low and high edge of the overlapped band portion, but at its middle.

5.5 Placement of Zoom Visibilities into Outputband Spectral Channels

For every frequency to be correlated, DiFX 2.6 allocates flat memory areas into which it stores the respective visibilities from all baselines and polarizations. These areas are accessed through multi-dimensional arrays of C++ pointers. Details were formerly undocumented. I have added in-depth documentation to the DiFX User Guide⁸.

For DiFX outputbands, the target outputband of a zoom band is specified explicitly

⁸DiFX User Guide, Appendix A, Internals for Developers, <https://svn.atnf.csiro.au/trac/difx/browser/doc/userguide/trunk>

by the *input* file (S 5.3). The spectral channel range into which to insert the zoom band visibility is implicit. It is deduced from the on-sky band edges of the zoom band relative to those of the outputband, the spectral resolution, and spectral averaging factor.

In the simplest implementation, DiFX 2.6 *mpifxcorr* can be retained almost as-is and merely a visibility data copying step from zoom band to outputband can be added.

The actual implementation, however, avoids the copying step and the redundant allocation of both zoom band and outputband visibility data areas. The initialization of the C++ memory pointer arrays was changed such that zoom band visibility data areas themselves are not allocated, and their pointers refer instead to the correct starting channels within the larger allocated outputband visibility data area (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Visibility data are redirected to the correct memory offset (top; C++ array `baselineoffset[[]]`) within a shared outputband, rather than into own separate data areas as in DiFX 2.6. Legacy autocorrelations and per-band weights are still allocated fully (bottom) for calibration related reasons.

Note that the trivial case of a one-to-one mapping redirects a recorded or zoom band onto itself, it being its own outputband. Behaviour in this case is identical to DiFX 2.6.

No remapping capability was added for legacy autocorrelation spectra and per-band data weights. The former are handled via the visibility data processing path (cf. § 5.9), the latter are needed as-is for deriving outputband weighted average weights (cf. § 5.8).

5.6 Frequency Averaging

DiFX 2.6 computes fringe-stopped auto spectra at high spectral resolution. Frequency averaging is applied on the fly while cross products are formed from pairs of auto spectra. All visibility data are internally kept in already averaged form.

With outputbands, the high resolution spectra of contributing zoom bands can have a spectral channel count that is not divisible by the averaging factor. An example is shown at the bottom of Figure 6. In the offline `difx2difx.py` implementation, averaging must be postponed until the entire high resolution outputband visibility has been formed. This incurs a large memory overhead. To avoid this in a native implementation the existing averaging loop was minimally augmented by bookkeeping of fractional channels.

5.7 Spectral Channel Flagging

Channels of an outputband may need to be flagged when they carry no meaningful phase information or their amplitude is hard to calibrate. These flagging conditions

are illustrated in Figure 6. When spectral averaging is used, it is possible that one output channel is the average of the channels of two contributing bands. In this case, T_{sys} , amplitude, and weight are ill defined for the resultant channel. In principle the information of which fraction of a channel originates from which recorded band could be stored in a user-readable file, however, the easiest approach is to flag such channels.

Figure 6: Flagging conditions for channels of an outputband. Channels that originate from edges of recorded bands carry no phase information (top). Channels that are an average across separate bands pose an amplitude calibration problem (bottom; averaging factor 4:1, amplitude of middle channel is poorly defined).

Vex2difx was extended to produce a flag file (`<jobname>.channelflags`) for each correlation job. Each line contains one flagging entry, consisting of an antenna name, MJD time range, numerical ID of a DiFX frequency, the range of channels (zero-based) to flag in that frequency, and lastly a flagging reason. For example:

```
AA 58230.158333 58230.161111 96 38 38 'edge'
AA 58230.158333 58230.161111 97 61 61 'edge'
NQ 58230.158333 58230.161111 96 38 38 'edge'
NQ 58230.158333 58230.161111 97 61 61 'edge'
```

Difx2fits was extended to import the channel flags directly into FITS-IDI table FG#1. For HOPS and the EHT HOPS pipeline, on the other hand, the user must manually translate channel flags into notch filter definitions in the configuration file.

5.8 Data Weights and Scaling

Data weights in DiFX consist of a decorrelation factor, and the fraction of valid sample data in an averaging period. Outputband channel ranges that originate from a certain zoom band have the channel amplitudes scaled independently by the weight of the underlying recorded band.

Standard DiFX also outputs weights alongside the visibility data. Under DiFX 2.6 these weights are the data weights of the recorded bands. For outputbands, these weights are the bandwidth-weighted sum of the data weights of the contributing (zoom-)bands, normalized by the total bandwidth of the final outputband.

This weighting accounts for potentially unequal data loss fractions in the underlying recorded bands. Such a case can occur when bands of the same station are separated to different physical media or into separate VDIF streams, and are subject to, e.g., disk failures during transport, or differences in network link characteristics during recording.

5.9 Handling of Autocorrelations

Autocorrelations are identical to zero-baseline visibility data. Rather than rework the legacy autocorrelation code in DiFX it was sufficient to make use of the already modified parts of DiFX related to visibility data processing (§ 5.5–5.8).

The DiFX 2.6 feature of “exhaustive autocorrelations” is reused in the outputbands implementation to elegantly compute autocorrelations. The respective v2d file parameter *exhaustiveAutocorrs* is enabled implicitly when *outputBandwidth* (§ 5.1) is in use.

For historical context, a desire for polarimetry with the EHT was an important driver for the DiFX 2.6 exhaustive autocorrelations feature. Because of backend design the EHT stations record polarizations separately, but autocorrelation code in DiFX can form cross-polarization products only between jointly recorded polarizations. The crosscorrelation code (visibility data processing) on the other hand is able to form products between any polarization and band. Injecting same-station “baselines” into the correlator setup was the programmatically simplest way of producing cross-polarization autocorrelations for such observations. It is fortunate that the same facility works for outputbands as well.

6 Preparing a DiFX Correlation Job

Residual delay offsets between recorded bands should be coarsely removed at the correlation stage so that they do not enter the outputbands. The delays can be determined with fringe finder scans, correlated without outputbands, using only recorded bands or custom zoom bands. Improved clocks are entered into *VEX* directly, or can be compensated as residuals via *v2d* parameter *deltaClock*.

If recorded bands have non-negligible delay offsets between polarizations they can be compensated via v2d parameter *freqClockOffs*. The delays can be determined for example using HOPS *fourfit* and control file parameter *est_pc_manual -16* or *est_pc_manual 16*, see the HOPS user guide. For example:

```
$ fourfit -ptx -b RE 1234 -P LL set est_pc_manual -16 pc_mode manual
*est: on: R1 - EF [RE] fq K pol LL ch a..d mode 16
if station E
  delay_offs_l abcd
    +3.390 +3.529 +3.330 +3.590
*est: delays converging (4)
```

```

$ fourfit -ptx -b RE 1234 -P RR set est_pc_manual -16 pc_mode manual
...
$ fourfit -ptx -b RE 1234 -P LR set est_pc_manual -16 pc_mode manual
...

```

The delays after some adjustments can be used in *freqClockOffs*, see the DiFX user guide. The first entry of *freqClockOffs* must be zero; the residual delay of the first HOPS channel must be lumped into the station clock offset (*deltaClock*), other values should be relative to the first frequency.

Once all residuals are sufficiently small one can enable outputbands correlation with the v2d parameter *outputBandwidth* as described in § 5.1.

7 Special Calibration Steps during Manual Post-Processing

In addition to basic flagging, there are two critical calibration steps for outputbands. Namely, a priori amplitude calibration with modified T_{sys}^* data that account for combined bands, and complex bandpass calibration to remove in-band discontinuities.

Note that for astrometric and geodetic VLBI it remains to be verified that the observables can be recovered accurately after such calibration. This verification is beyond the scope of this report and remains the subject of a paper.

7.1 Flagging

In case of FITS-IDI data the FITS file comes pre-populated with channel flag records for all outputbands, see § 5.7. For HOPS, however, a suitable notch filter configuration must be derived manually.

7.2 Calibration of Flux Density Scale

Calibration is based on a time series of station T_{sys}^* or T_{sys} measurements, and a static DPFU and gain-elevation curve model. The T_{sys}^* data are usually determined over frequency ranges identical to the recorded VLBI bands. Even with traditional DiFX zoom band correlation these data may not be adequate as they are based on a wider bandwidth than the visibility data, but the outside-of-zoomband portions can have (and rarely indeed do have) RFI or atmospheric absorption that elevate T_{sys}^* . A related complication occurs with outputbands that combine portions of several recorded bands.

A substitute T_{sys}^* can be formed for an outputband by two approaches: 1) taking the weighted average T_{sys}^* of the associated recorded bands, weighted by their utilized-bandwidth fractions, or 2) re-analyzing the single dish calibration spectra over the exact frequency range of the outputband. Both approaches are under consideration for EHT VLBI, but neither is currently automated, nor is there any example script in DiFX outputbands at this time.

7.3 Calibration of In-Band Amplitude and Phase

Certain mismatches between recorded bands propagate into the outputband and produce discontinuities in the visibility amplitudes and phases inside the band. The issue is illustrated in Figures 7.

Figure 7: An illustration of bandpass discontinuities in outputbands. The two simulated HOPS *fourfit*-like plots for outputbands of 1000 MHz (top) and 60 MHz (bottom) show drops in amplitude (blue) related to ALMA filterbank edges, and show offsets in visibility phase (red) caused by delay offsets between ALMA filterbank channels. The original recorded bands are 1 x 2048 MHz at APEX and 32 x overlapped 62.5 MHz at ALMA. The discontinuities in the outputbands occur at spectral regions where two different recorded bands are joined. Similar discontinuities are likely to occur with NOEMA 64 x 64 MHz.

Discontinuities appear because of station(s) with narrower bands such as phased ALMA or NOEMA. Some of the phase or clock offsets between filterbank bands can be removed during correlation (§ 6). Certain spectral channels known a priori to be affected during outputband processing can be flagged (§ 7.1). Other phase differences, however, and in particular amplitude characteristics of the outputbands, need a complex bandpass calibration. Even though the station analog IF signals may have smooth band shape and phase, the recorded narrower bands after e.g. filterbank processing do not necessarily “align” in their amplitudes and phases/delays. Alignment of recorded bands can be poor due to per-band digital signal processing differences in a VLBI backend, or in a phased array correlator and VLBI formatter, such as

- (a) independent 2-bit thresholding, i.e., numerical gain control for each band recorded from a polyphase filterbank (PFB) or a bank of digital downconverters (DDC)
- (b) incorrect/random initial phases of the numerical LO in DDCs

- (c) no return-to-phase when DDC are re-tuned
- (d) shifts in per channel timestamp propagation, n-sample data shifts
- (e) array phasing system does not connect channels
- (f) chosen DiFX spectral output resolution is narrow relative to steepness of the digital filters in the backend, filter cut offs at edge channels

Complex bandpass calibration on a continuum source can remove residual instrumental-like bandpass effects that are due to several of the above mismatches.

Time-varying bandpass solutions may have to be derived if the backend frequency setup is changed during the VLBI observation, or the members of the phased array or the phasing change.

Future study is needed and should inspect whether a single bandpass calibration remains stable throughout an observation, whether such a calibration works in position-switched spectral emission line observations, and whether geodetic VLBI observables are affected by residual in-band phase discontinuities or residual mismatched delays between bands.

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